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Letter to the editor

Sexual dysfunction in uncomplicated diabetic men: Positive association with insulin therapy

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Erectile Dysfunction(ED), the inability to achieve and / or to maintain an erection for a sufficiently long period of time to permit satisfactory sexual intercourse has been attributed to diabetic nephropathy in diabetic patients [1, 2]. ED showed a positive correlation with age after 65 years, history of diabetes of more than 10 years and was not correlated to the type of diabetes mellitus and diabetic therapy [3, 4, 5]. In one study the prevalence of ED is lower in type 1 diabetic patient. [6]. Orgasmic dysfunction was correlated positively with the duration of diabetes but not with the type of received by the patients [7]. The prevalence of erectile dysfunction amongst diabetic men in a hospital clinic population has been reported to be between 35 and 40 % [8, 9]. Also ED has been reported in up to 75% of diabetic men [8-12].

The aim of this paper is to report a positive correlation between ED in small series of relatively health patients with uncomplicated diabetes. From January to march 2003, 28 male diabetic patients attending the outpatient of general hospital in Baghdad, were asked to complete a questionnaire of 11 questions about their disease and sexual problems. All the patients answered the questions

completely. We excluded any patient with sexual dysfunction prior to the diabetic illness and other associated medical condition. The age of patients ranged from 19 to 50 years (mean 35.5y.) Twenty of them (71%) were married and 8 (29%) were single.

Twelve patients (43%) were diagnosed as diabetic type 1 and 16 patients (57%) were diabetic type 2. The diagnosis depended on the international classification of the diabetes mellitus & was done by a specialist in endocrinology. 16 patients (57%) were on insulin treatment, 9 patients (32%) on hypoglycemic agents and 3 patients (11%) on mixed treatment.

The answers were analyzed and statistical methods of percentages and chi-square had been used. 10 patients (35.5%) complained from ED and one patient (3.5%) complained from lack of interest, while 17 patients (61%) did not have sexual dysfunction. Among patients with sexual dysfunction, 5 patients (46%) on insulin therapy, 3 patients (27%) on hypoglycemic agents and the remainder 3 patients (27%) were on mixed treatments.

In this series significant numbers of diabetic men were excluded because of

prior sexual dysfunction and other medical disorders.

The lack of sexual interest was described by only one patient (3.5%). It appeared that premature ejaculation was considered to remain intact. The most interesting finding of this study was that half of patients with ED were on insulin therapy which is inconsistent with other studies which found that it is lower in type 1 diabetic patients [2]

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